

Table 2. Yield of 4 new upland rice varieties in farmers' fields in Kambia District, Sierra Leone.

Variety	1986-87				1987-88			
	Kamaranka	Funkia	Petifu	Mean	Gberika	Rochain	Rochint	Mean
ROK17	2.2	1.9	2.1	2.1	2.9	2.4	2.4	2.5
ROK18	2.0	2.8	2.3	2.4	2.8	2.8	2.3	2.4
ROK19	2.8	2.3	2.0	2.2	2.4	2.0	2.3	2.2
ROK20	2.4	2.1	2.3	2.3	2.7	2.2	2.4	2.3
ROK16 (check)	1.8	1.6	1.8	1.7	1.5	1.3	1.7	1.5
CV (%)	12.2	14.6	18.2	15	19.7	22.9	14.4	19
LSD (0.05)	8.2	8.2	8.2	8.2	8.2	8.1	8.2	8.2
Soil	Sandy loam	Loam	Gravelly clay loam		Clay loam	Sandy loam	Loam	
pH (water)	5.0	4.9	5.1		5.5	4.8	5.0	
CEC (meq/100g)	11.4	10.2	13.2		15.1	9.9	11.1	
Organic C (%)	1.2	0.9	1.4		2.1	0.8	1.8	
Total rainfall (mm)	2,156				2,256			

and South Sierra Leone. ROK17 is preferred by North Sierra Leone farmers because it is awnless, which makes threshing with the feet less painful. It also has better cooking and eating qualities.

ROK18, ROK19, and ROK20 are short-duration varieties superior to ROK16 in plant type, disease resistance, and phenotypic acceptability. They are recommended for the low rainfall areas of the north. Grain size ranges from slender to medium bold, as preferred by northern farmers. □

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

ASD18, a blast (Bl)-resistant rice variety for Tamil Nadu

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Bl-resistant, short-duration, medium-slender rice culture AS34011, selected from the cross ADT31/IR50, was released as ASD18 by the Tamil Nadu G.D. Naidu Agricultural University in Jan 1991. It is recommended as an alternative to IR50 and TKM9 for summer (Mar-Jun), first season (Jun-Sep), and second season (Nov-Feb) planting.

ASD18 is 90 cm tall with 105-110 d growth duration. Mean grain yield was 7.3 t/ha over 6 yr at RRS, 5.7 t/ha in multilocation trials over 2 yr at seven research stations throughout Tamil Nadu, and 5.9 t/ha under Adaptive Research Trials (ART) in 52 farmers' fields. Total dry mass was 18.2 t/ha (8.5 t grain and 9.7 t straw) at Ambasamudram; potential grain yield was 10.1 t/ha under ART.

It is resistant to Bl and moderately resistant to sheath rot and tungro (Table 1). It is resistant to brown planthopper and stem borer and moderately resistant to gall midge and leafhopper (Table 2). □

Table 1. Reaction of ASD18 to major diseases in Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Reaction ^a						
	Blast			Sheath rot ASD-N	Sheath blight ASD-A	RTV	
	ADT-A	DBE-A	ASD-N			ADT-A	CBE-A
ASD18	1	3	3	5	7	4	5
IR50	3	9	9	7	9	5	3
TKM9	3	7	7	7	9	8	9

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice (SES) scale. N = natural condition, A = artificial condition, ADT = Aduthurai, ASD = Ambasamudram, CBE = Coimbatore.

Table 2. Reaction of ASD18 to major pests in Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Reaction ^a						
	BPH		SB		GM	LF	
	ADT-A	ASD-A	ASD-N	MDU-A	MDU-A	CBE-N	ASD-A
ASD18	3	5	3	0	5	7	5
IR50	9	5	3		3	9	7
TKM9	9	9	3		0	9	7

^aBY SES. BPH = brown planthopper, SB = stem borer, GM = gall midge, LF = leafhopper. ADT = Aduthurai, ASD = Ambasamudram, MDU = Madurai, CBE = Coimbatore. N = natural condition, A = artificial condition, (-) = not tested.

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed lowland

Three new varieties of short-duration rice released in Cambodia

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Short-duration rices (120 d or less) cover almost 25% of Cambodia's rice area. In the dry season, they are grown in about 10% of the area, either irrigated or with receding water. In the wet season, they are grown in about 15% of the area as a rainfed lowland crop.

A number of traditional early varieties

are planted; varieties such as IR36, IR42, IR50, and IR66, and some IR-based

varieties introduced via Vietnam (such as NN3) are also popular. To identify more

adapted varieties, IRRI-Cambodia Project trials were conducted in 13 provinces over four seasons 1989-90.

Table 1. Yield of 3 new varieties during 1989 and 1990 wet seasons in Cambodia.

Location	Field ^a (t/ha)							
	IR66		IR72		Kru		Check	
	1989	1990	1989	1990	1989	1990	1989	1990
Tonle Bati	-	5.1 ab	-	5.2 ab	-	5.7 a	-	4.8 bc
Por Lors	-	3.6 a	-	2.6 b	-	2.9 ab	-	2.9 ab
Ballang	4.8	3.8 ab	4.9	3.6 ac	5.2	2.5 be	4.1	4.0 a
Day Eth	2.7 be	5.1 bc	2.9 bd	4.7 bc	3.9 a	5.8 a	3.1 ab	4.8 c
Prey Kabas	3.6	3.6	1.8	3.2	2.9	3.2	1.8	2.9
Kbal Po	-	3.2 a	-	3.0 ab	-	3.2 ab	-	2.8 b
Chhbar Mom	5.4 ab	3.3	5.4 ac	3.2	5.3 ac	3.7	4.6 ae	2.5
Kompong Siem	-	2.5 bc	-	2.6 bc	-	3.0 a	-	2.7 b
Prey Khmer	5.4 ae	5.1 ab	5.0 be	4.9 ab	6.6 a	5.4 a	5.9 ac	4.9 ab
Toul Bakha	4.0 ab	3.5 a	4.2 a	3.3 a	4.1 ab	3.1 ab	3.2 bd	2.8 ac
Kirivong	-	4.2 b	-	3.6 bc	-	4.0 bc	-	4.2 b
Chumcar Daung	5.7 ad	5.2 ab	6.6 ab	5.4 ab	6.5 ab	5.2 a	5.7 ad	4.8 b
Slakou	-	2.0 ad	-	1.7 d	-	2.2 ab	-	1.9 bd
Kap Srau	-	4.7 ab	-	4.6 ad	-	4.0 cd	-	4.8 a
Prey Phdau	5.9 ab	4.5 ab	5.1 a	3.9 c	4.8 ac	5.1 a	4.1 be	4.6 ab
Ta Saang	2.1 ad	2.5 bc	2.7 ad	2.0 bd	2.3 be	2.7 a	2.7 ad	2.4 ac
Bek Chan	5.9	5.6 a	5.9	5.0 ac	6.8	5.2 ah	6.6	3.9 d
Tuk Will	2.3	2.0 ab	2.0	1.8 cd	2.3	2.1 a	1.7	1.6 d
Toul Lapao	-	1.5	-	1.3	-	1.3	-	1.3
Toul Chrem Chrom	-	1.9 ac	-	2.7 ab	-	1.5 bc	-	2.1 ac

^a Any two means having a common letter at a location in a year are not significantly different by DMRT.

Of 20 entries tested in 1989 and 10 in 1990, IR66, IR72, and IR13429-150-3-2-1-2 (named Kru) were best (Table 1). They yielded 4 t/ha across 13 locations during dry season 1990, against 3.2 t/ha of the highest yielding check. (IR36 and IR64 were the check varieties.) In 38 trials over four seasons and 2 yr, IR66, IR72, and Kru yielded 4.2, 4.1, and 4.4 t/ha, respectively, compared to 3.7 t/ha from the check. Other agronomic characters are given in Table 2.

These three varieties were tested in farmers' fields in 13 provinces, with a traditional early variety added as local check. At some of 75 locations, IR66, IR72, and Kru yielded more than 6 t/ha (average 2.5-2.8 t/ha). A few hundred tons of seed were multiplied by the farmers themselves during 1990. □

Table 2. Grain yield and ancillary characters of 3 early varieties in dry season (13 locations) and wet season (20 locations) trials in Cambodia, 1990.

Variety	Duration (d)		Plant height (cm)		Panicle length (cm)		Grains/panicle		Panicles/m ²		Yield (t/ha)		PAcp ^a	
	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet
IR66	106±1.3	110±0.8	75±2.5	85.8±1.5	21.3±0.10	22.8±0.4	89±8.4	101±6.0	329±15.0	286±15.7	4.0	3.9	3.2±0.6	2.07±0.42
IR72	115±1.2	114±0.8	72±2.5	81.8±1.9	21.9±0.46	21.7±0.4	85±9.5	86±4.1	306±18.6	292±15.8	4.0	3.6	2.0±0.8	2.21±0.40
KRU	112±1.0	113±0.8	75±2.6	83.0±1.9	22.9±0.46	21.4±0.3	88±11.0	90±5.34	373±23.0	317±17.5	4.1	3.9	2.7±0.7	2.14±0.34
Check	111±1.2	111±1.0	77±3.0	87.8±2.0	21.7±0.51	22.4±0.5	75±14.0	80±3.8	308±19.6	291±15.5	3.2	3.6	4.0±0.5	2.86±0.43

^aPAcp = phenotypic acceptability.

Integrated germplasm improvement—tidal wetland

Performance of short-duration rice varieties in tidal swamps of Indonesia

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We screened 23 promising lines to identify short-duration rice varieties that yielded well in sulfate acid soils at Unit Tatas substation, Central Kalimantan, 1987-88 (Table 1). Seedlings (21 d old) were transplanted at 25- x 25-cm spacing in 7.5-m² plots in a randomized block design with four replications. Fertilizer

Table 1. Some Chemical Characteristics of acid sulfate soils at Unit Tatas Substation, Central Kalimantan, Indonesia.

Characteristic	Depth	
	0-15 cm	>15 cm
pH H ₂ O	4.0	4.0
Organic C (%)	2.8	1.7
Total N (%)	0.4	0.2
P Bray (ppm)	1.7	1.3
K (meq/100 g)	0.2	0.1
Ca (meq/100 g)	0.4	0.3
Mg (meq/100g)	1.2	0.9
Na (meq/100 g)	0.2	0.3
CEC (meq/100 g)	22.0	37.0
Al (meq/100 g)	14.0	16.0
H (meq/100 g)	1.0	0.8
Texture (%)		
- Clay	37	45
- Silt	62	54
- Sand	1	1

was 90-60-50 kg NPK/ha. All the P and K, and half the N were applied basally at transplanting; the remaining N was applied 30 d after transplanting. Pest infestation was measured at peak incidence.

BW267-3 had the highest grain yield, followed by CR61-7039-236, IR6023-10-1-1, and IR19661-13-3-2 (Table 2). BW267-3 and IR6023-10-1-1 are intermediate tall, IR19661-13-3-2, and CR261-7039-236 are semidwarf. These four short-duration lines have the highest number of panicles/m² and can be developed for the tidal swamps. Grain of IR19661-13-3-2, IR6023-10-1-1, and BW267-3 are long, slender; those of